

DIRECTIONS D3.2:

Report on methods for selecting EMT protection studies

May 2026

This deliverable forms part of the DIRECTIONS project, funded by the Energy Transition Fund, FOD Economy, Belgium.
Contributors: A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem.

With support from:

Contents

1	Executive summary	1
2	Introduction	3
3	Modelling accuracy requirements for HVDC protection design studies	6
3.1	Introduction	6
3.2	Estimation of accuracy requirements	8
3.2.1	Estimation based on production cost analysis	8
3.2.2	Estimation based on performance analysis	10
3.3	Impact of MMC modelling accuracy on DCCB parameters	11
3.3.1	Case study description and assessment method	11
3.3.2	System component modelling	13
3.3.3	DCCB current contributions	14
3.3.4	Impact of fault parameters on DCCB parameters	14
3.4	Conclusion	14
4	Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies	17
4.1	Introduction	17
4.2	Model requirements for remote MMC	19
4.2.1	Conditions allowing use of reduced order models	20
4.2.2	Decision on remote MMC model	24
4.3	Validation of model selection requirement	24
4.3.1	Study case for model selection requirement	25
4.3.2	Impact of system configuration and parameters	27
4.3.3	Impact of adjacent cable/OHL on local zone	29
4.4	Conclusion	30
5	Identification of critical simulation cases	31
5.1	Critical cases for protection design	31
5.1.1	Critical converter	31
5.1.2	Critical power flows	31

5.1.3	Critical fault type and location	32
6	Conclusion	34
	Bibliography	35

Chapter 1

Executive summary

Introduction

This report presents the second part of the outcomes of DIRECTIONS WP3 on *Methods for Selecting EMT Protection Studies*. The aim of this document is to provide methods for efficiently performing studies involving EMT-type simulations, based on *T3.2 – Efficient EMT-Type Simulations for Protection Design of Energy Hubs*. The results of this task can subsequently be used in EMT-type studies, such as the design and validation of HVDC protection systems, including electrical energy hubs.

Motivation

As the scale and complexity of HVDC systems continue to grow, performing exhaustive EMT simulations for protection studies, such as component-level parameter specification and validation, becomes increasingly extensive and time-consuming. Therefore, there is a strong need for methodologies that enable efficient and effective EMT studies while maintaining sufficient accuracy.

Key contributions

Modelling accuracy requirements for HVDC protection design studies

To perform HVDC protection studies more efficiently, this report proposes an efficient method for selecting a modular multilevel converter (MMC) model, as a key component of HVDC grids. This is achieved by determining the accuracy requirements of component models. Firstly, it estimates

an accuracy requirement for protection studies based on i) a cost-based approach, and ii) a performance-based approach analysis, which recommends guidelines for selecting models. Secondly, it investigated the influence of the different MMC models for protection studies, such as DCCB sizing. The key finding with respect to the MMC model is that the average model of the converter (Type 5) mostly satisfies the requirements of protection studies, which is computationally less expensive than the other detailed models. Furthermore, the impact of the local MMC model is more significant than the remote MMC, highlighting the necessity for more precise modeling of the local one.

Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies

To reduce the complexity of protection studies, particularly during the design stage, it may not be necessary to model all MMCs at the same level of detail in the system. A novel methodology based on an analytical approximation is introduced to define the boundary conditions for the region of the system where a simplified MMC model can be used without compromising the accuracy of the region under study. It uses the MMC's fault-current contribution in areas beyond the direct area of interest. This approach provides insights into how much of the grid can be modeled with less detail for studies of specific areas and time scales. The key finding is that for a converter located in a remote area, a simpler model, such as RLC or a current source, can be used to further reduce system complexity for efficient simulation without sacrificing accuracy. This remote area is characterized by cable length and DC inductor value.

Identification of critical simulation cases

Furthermore, identifying the critical simulation cases for protection studies, such as protection component-level design, can significantly reduce the number of simulations required and improve the efficiency of the design process. To address this, a method for selecting the critical fault type and location, the critical power flow, and the critical converter is proposed to reduce the number of design scenarios.

Chapter 2

Introduction

Transitioning from conventional point-to-point HVDC systems toward multiterminal HVDC (MTDC) networks and Electrical Energy Hubs (EEHs) significantly increases overall system size and complexity. This increased complexity has a substantial impact across different types of studies, particularly HVDC protection studies, where detailed Electromagnetic Transient (EMT) simulations are required to accurately capture fast-transient phenomena. Compared with traditional RMS simulations commonly used in conventional AC system studies, EMT simulations are considerably more computationally intensive and require higher computational resources and simulation time. The challenge becomes even more critical in MTDC grids that include a large number of Modular Multilevel Converters (MMCs), as a key component. In such systems, a wide range of EMT studies is required across different protection studies, including design, validation, and commissioning. As the scale and complexity of these systems continue to grow, performing exhaustive EMT simulations for all possible operating conditions and contingencies is time-consuming. Consequently, there is a strong need for methodologies that enable efficient and effective EMT studies while maintaining sufficient accuracy and ensuring that critical scenarios are not overlooked. Therefore, this deliverable presents several methods to improve the efficiency of EMT-based studies for MTDC systems.

In Chapter 3, an effective method for determining the accuracy requirements of component models used in HVDC protection studies. Then, it is used to select computationally efficient MMC models. This is achieved by performing a sensitivity analysis of key DCCB parameters, such as current, voltage, and energy, with respect to different system and fault conditions.

In Chapter 4, a novel analytical method is proposed to approximate the boundary conditions defining the region of the system where a simplified MMC model can be used without compromising the accuracy of the region under study. The key finding is that for a converter located in a remote area, a simpler model, such as RLC or a current source, can be used to further reduce

Figure 2.1: Workflow and structure of deliverable

system complexity for efficient simulation without sacrificing accuracy.

In Chapter 5, a methodology for identifying critical simulation cases is proposed. This approach ensures that the selected design parameters remain valid across all relevant scenarios while minimizing the total number of cases that need to be evaluated.

Figure 2.1 summarizes the content of this deliverable and positions the subsequent chapters with respect to the proposed protection system design methodology.

The content in this deliverable is based on the following paper:

- Abolfazl Mohammadi, Geraint Chaffey and Dirk Van Hertem, “Modelling Accuracy Requirements for HVDC Protection Design Studies,” 2025 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT Europe), Valletta, Malta, 2025, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ISGTEurope64741.2025.11305690 [1].
- A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. Van Hertem, “Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies,” in 22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission, Berlin, Germany, April 2026. [2]
- A. Mohammadi, M. Van Deyck, G. Chaffey, D. Van Hertem, “Hybrid Analytical–EMT Method for HVDC Protection System Component-Level Design,” arXiv [3]

Chapter 3

Modelling accuracy requirements for HVDC protection design studies

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey and D. Van Hertem, “Modelling Accuracy Requirements for HVDC Protection Design Studies,” 2025 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT Europe), Valletta, Malta, 2025, pp. 1–5, doi: 10.1109/ISGTEurope64741.2025.11305690 [1].

3.1 Introduction

Multiterminal HVDC (MTDC) systems present a promising approach for future power transmission, enabling efficient long-distance bulk power transfer, interconnection of asynchronous AC networks, and integration of offshore wind energy. However, one of the main technical challenges in HVDC grids is protecting against DC faults [4]. This is due to the characteristics of the DC fault current, such as the lack of natural zero crossings and rapid rise. Faults in large MTDC systems should be detected and isolated quickly using a suitable protection system, e.g., using an HVDC circuit breaker (DCCB). HVDC protection system component sizing, such as for a DCCB, is complex due to the numerous parameters and their interactions with other grid components, e.g., converter fault-ride-through. Sizing requires detailed EMT simulations and high-fidelity component modelling. However, to ensure scalability, simpler models are preferred. It is necessary to ensure the suitable accuracy of the applied model during design and verification. As the

DCCB costs, primarily influenced by CAPEX, significantly affect the total DC protection cost. This ensures the device fulfils its functional requirements without being over-designed or under-designed [5].

Protection studies of large MTDC systems could be categorised into system-level and component-level analysis [6]. ‘System-level’ refers to aspects such as system topology design and component placement, which necessitate high-level studies like power flow, often employing simplified models, e.g., the steady-state model [7]. On the other hand, ‘component-level’ refers to specific studies that focus on the specification of a component, including the design of protection algorithms and component sizing. These studies are typically performed using EMT simulations to represent the real system to a sufficient level of accuracy for the phenomena under study [8]. Moreover, system design can be categorised into stages, ranging from system-level to commissioning, for which the study’s objective, modelling, and tool requirements differ [8].

The requirements for protection studies, such as sizing a DCCB, can deviate from their true values due to uncertainties, including model inaccuracy, numerical errors, parameter uncertainty, and other unknown factors. For instance, using (over-)simplified component models, such as cables or MMCs, may lead to wrong component sizing, such as DCCB, surge arrester, line inductance, etc. There is extensive research on component modelling for HVDC applications, such as for MMCs [9], [10], [11], where different models for half-bridge MMCs are investigated for HVDC protection studies. Also, various DCCB models [12] and cable models [13] are compared and analysed. Furthermore, some works cover the analysis of parameter uncertainty on MMC and cable for transient studies [14], cable parameter uncertainties determination [15] and impact of these parameters in protection algorithms [16]. However, the accuracy requirements of component models for HVDC protection system studies have not been studied.

When sizing a protection component, minimising the investment cost and meeting the functional requirements are desired. However, the variance from true design requirements depends on various factors, e.g., the inaccuracy of the converter or cable model can affect protection algorithms tuning [16]. To account for these variances, a design buffer is typically added during the engineering design process (Fig. 3.1, adapted from [17]), which can lead to increased investment costs and potentially compromise performance. Therefore, this chapter aims to guide the determination of the accuracy requirement for the component model for component-level studies, such as the sizing of the DCCB. To achieve this, an analysis based on i) a cost-based approach and ii) a performance-based approach is conducted to estimate the necessary level of accuracy in Section 3.2. Following this, in Section 3.3, different types of MMC models are compared based on DCCB

Figure 3.1: Concept of design margin for protection equipment to cover the uncertainty related to the determination of the true requirement, e.g., DCCB maximum current (adapted from [17])

parameters under varying system and fault conditions to determine their accuracy.

3.2 Estimation of accuracy requirements

Minimising investment costs and fulfilling functional requirements when sizing the component for protection design is challenging, given that many factors are involved. For instance, modelling inaccuracies, parameter uncertainties, and other unknowns affect the determination of true requirements of a specific study (as shown in Fig. 3.1). One example of an HVDC protection component that needs to be designed carefully is the DCCB, as its design depends on other components' characteristics, e.g. MMC [18] and line inductance (L_{dc}) [4]. Sizing the DCCB refers to specifying the electrical DCCB parameters, such as operating time, voltage withstand capability, line inductor value, operating time, and interruption capability (maximum current and energy) [4]. To gain insight into the accuracy requirements for protection component sizing, the following methodology is applied:

1. Estimation of the accuracy requirement based on production cost analysis
2. Estimation of the accuracy requirement based on performance analysis.

3.2.1 Estimation based on production cost analysis

One approach to estimating an accuracy requirement is to evaluate the cost of adding a design margin to the protection system. For instance, specifying the DCCB maximum current interruption, a margin of ε_i should be added to avoid under-design. This ensures the true current lies within required

bounds, though it may lead to overdesign. Ideally, a detailed model (such as a vendor model) would eliminate the need for additional design margin related to modelling error. Nonetheless, often the vendor models are unavailable, or the required details of the model remain uncertain. To address this, if the relationship between modelling error and associated cost is known, the necessary accuracy can be estimated by approximating the investment cost of the component. To do so, as an approximation, the material cost of the electrical components of a hybrid DCCB (C_B) can be assumed as a sum of its elements [19], i.e. of the cost of power electronic components such as IGBTs (C_{PE}), inductor cost (C_L), MOV cost (C_{MOV}) and an additional constant cost (C_C) in (3.1). The cost of each element is a portion of the final cost, and they can be represented as a weight ($\omega_i = C_i/C_B$), where $i \in \{PE, L, MOV, C\}$, to extract more specific information from it.

$$C_B = C_{PE} + C_L + C_{MOV} + C_C \quad (3.1)$$

To evaluate the impact of the deviation of voltage (ε_u) and current (ε_i) from the reference model on the DCCB cost, the Delta Cost Ratio (ΔCR) is used as the difference between the cost of an arbitrary modelling (C_{B1}), where a simplified model is used for a component, with base case cost C_B as (3.3) (derived in Appendix B).

$$\Delta CR = \frac{C_{B1} - C_B}{C_B} \quad (3.2)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\approx \omega_{MOV} \varepsilon_i^2 \\ &\quad + [\omega_{PE}(\varepsilon_u + 1) + \omega_L + 2\omega_{MOV}] \varepsilon_i \\ &\quad + \omega_{PE} \varepsilon_u \end{aligned} \quad (3.3)$$

According to (3.3), the voltage and current errors result in additional design costs, which depend on the weighted value (ω_i) associated with each element in (3.1). The imposed cost can be estimated by identifying the errors and applying (3.3). If the resulting (ΔCR) is acceptable, the errors can be considered acceptable from a cost perspective.

Alternatively, by setting a satisfactory value for ΔCR , the acceptable ε_i and ε_u can be estimated using (2). It is worth mentioning that the maximum acceptable ΔCR mainly depends on the design stage. A higher uncertainty buffer may be accepted for system-level studies. However, for the final design or component-level stage, a much lower uncertainty buffer can be accepted, indicating that a more accurate model is required for this stage. Since the maximum acceptable error of variables depends on ω_i values, two approaches can be used. The first approach considers the worst-case scenario when values ω_i are selected (i.e., $0.1 \leq \omega_i \leq 0.9$) so that they provide the stringent conditions for acceptable ε_i and ε_u , as shown in Fig. 3.2 (left).

Figure 3.2: Cost-based approach: acceptable error values for current and voltage for different levels of ΔCR ; (left): a worst-case condition, where values ω_i are selected (i.e., $0.1 \leq \omega_i \leq 0.9$) so that they provide the stringent conditions for ε_i and ε_u ; *Right*: a realistic case where values of ω_i are selected so that they reflect a realistic cost weight (i.e. $\omega = [0.4, 0.2, 0.3, 0.1]$ estimated based on results in [5], [19]).

In this plot, each curve consists of two lines with different ω_i values. The second approach selects the values of ω_i so that they reflect a realistic cost weight (e.g., $\omega = [0.4, 0.25, 0.25, 0.1]$ estimated based on results in [5], [19]), Fig. 3.2 (right).

3.2.2 Estimation based on performance analysis

Similar to the cost analysis, more accurate results are required for the final design stage than for the pre-specification or conceptual studies. The necessary accuracy for the component model can be estimated based on specific performance metrics that meet the functional requirements. For instance, the speed of the protection algorithm can be considered as a one performance indicator. Of course, there are others as well, such as reliability and dependability indicators; however, the scope of this work is an introduction to how performance indicators can be used to determine accuracy requirements. Therefore, depending on the required performances, the required accuracy can be determined accordingly. Considering basic protection algorithms such as overcurrent and undervoltage, the conceptual formulation used to give an approximate indication of the speed (operating time) can be considered as follows (derived in Appendix C):

$$t_{relay} \approx \frac{a}{b} \cdot \frac{1}{1 \pm \varepsilon_b} \quad (3.4)$$

where, for overcurrent protection, $a = I_{th} - I_0$ and $b = \frac{di_0}{dt}$. For undervolt-

age protection, $a = U_{th} - U_0$ and $b = \left| \frac{du_0}{dt} \right|$. The I_{th} and U_{th} are overcurrent and undervoltage threshold values, and I_0 and U_0 are the pre-fault current and voltage, respectively. The ε_b is the error of parameter b . Based on Fig. 3.3, by setting an acceptable deviation for t_{relay} , the boundary error of parameter b can be estimated, which estimates the maximum acceptable error. A similar method can be applied to fault interruption time as another conceptual performance metric. For simplicity, by assuming the voltage across the DCCB is approximated as a constant value, U_{CB} , and also neglecting the cable voltage during the fault, the fault interruption time can be estimated by (3.5) based on [20]. However, many assumptions on (3.5) need to be validated. Still, it serves as an example to illustrate the rough relationship between the operating time of DCCB and the required accuracy for voltage and current.

$$t_{clear} \approx \tau \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{I_p}{U_{CB} - U_B} R \right) \quad (3.5)$$

In (4), $\tau = \frac{L}{R}$, where L and R are the equivalent inductance and resistance, respectively, throughout the fault current path. I_p is the peak fault current, and U_B is the bus voltage. By including the error of current and voltage in (3.5), their relationship with the t_{relay} error (ε_{tc}) can be determined as (3.6). Therefore, by setting an acceptable value for ε_{tc} , the required error for current and voltage can be estimated. Similar to Fig. 2, by plotting the t_{relay} versus ε_i and ε_u , different levels of ε_{tc} can be estimated.

$$t_{clear0} \pm \varepsilon_{tc} \approx \tau \cdot \ln \left(1 + \frac{I_{p0} \pm \varepsilon_i}{(U_{CB0} - U_{B0}) \pm \varepsilon_u} R \right) \quad (3.6)$$

3.3 Impact of MMC modelling accuracy on DCCB parameters

This section presents a case study to investigate the impact of the accuracy of different modelling approaches for MMC on the DCCB parameters through sensitivity analysis under various system and fault parameters, aiming to identify critical cases and evaluate the impact of model accuracy.

3.3.1 Case study description and assessment method

An example of a three-terminal HVDC system (Fig. 3.4) with a symmetrical monopole configuration is considered to evaluate the impact of converter modelling accuracy on DCCB parameters, focusing on the system-level studies. By applying a fault on cable 1, MMC-A (local) and MMC-R (remote), along with the discharge current of cable 2, mainly contribute to the CB1

Figure 3.3: Performance-based approach: operating time of overcurrent ($a = I_{th} - I_0$, $b = di/dt$) and undervoltage ($a = U_0 - U_{th}$, $b = du/dt$) protection versus error of input argument (b).

Figure 3.4: An example of a three-terminal symmetrical monopole HVDC system (per-pole representation).

current. In that case, the impact on modelling accuracy of local and remote MMCs can be investigated in relation to the DCCB design parameters. Two different cases are considered to analyse the different modelling impact of local and remote MMC. The MMC model varies for each case and is compared with the base case, where all MMCs are represented as a detailed model. The simulations are performed in PSCAD using a time step of $10 \mu s$. All test cases are simulated under the same simulation environments and conditions for a fair comparison.

For comparison of the results, the relative error in (6) is considered and normalised with respect to the base model.

$$\varepsilon = \frac{x - x^*}{x^*} \times 100 \quad (3.7)$$

Figure 3.5: Example of the impact of different modelling of MMC and their location on the DCCB current: I_{CB} using different models (M_0 to M_3) for MMC for a PP fault on cable 1 ($p=1\%$, $R_f = 0.01$) without DCCB operation.

3.3.2 System component modelling

Several types of MMC models, from Type 1 to Type 6, have been introduced for different applications [21]. However, for system-level studies of HVDC protection application, Types 1 and 2 are not likely to be applicable due to the high complexity [22]. Hence, model Types-3 to 6 are considered in this comparison. Moreover, Type 3 and Type 4 models exhibit similar behaviour when the internal parameters of MMC are not of interest [23]. Therefore, commonly used models from each type are selected as examples. The following models for MMC are used; M_0 : Type 4 [23], M_1 : Type 5 [9], M_2 : Type 6 [10] and M_3 : Type 6 [11]. M_2 and M_3 are RLC models, where M_2 has blocking capability, while M_3 is a simplified RLC model without blocking capability. Detailed model parameters are applied based on [18]. Moreover, the internal overcurrent protection of the MMC blocks all submodules in case of a DC fault, when the arm current exceeds 1.5 pu [18]. A ± 320 kV XLPE cable in symmetrical monopole system [24] with frequency dependent phase model (FDPM) is used, given that it is the most detailed commercially available model [24]. The DCCB is modelled as a simplified generic model (Type 5 [23]) as it meets the system-level studies requirements, such as DCCB sizing studies, as described in [25]. The characteristics of Metal Oxide Varistor (MOV) and parameters for DCCB, such as operating time and maximum interruption time, are provided in [25] and [26], respectively.

3.3.3 DCCB current contributions

To assess the accuracy impact of different MMC models and their locations (local and remote) on DCCB current (I_{CB}), the impact of four types of MMC models for both local and remote MMCs is compared in Fig. 3.5. Comparing the different models impact shows that as expected simplified models shows less inaccuracy as time pass. Comparing the results of the local (upper plot) and remote (lower plot) MMCs models reveals that the local MMC modelling has a more significant impact on the accuracy of the DCCB current.

3.3.4 Impact of fault parameters on DCCB parameters

This part further investigates the influence of fault parameters, such as fault resistance, fault location, and line inductance, with a sensitivity to evaluate the local and remote MMC models' accuracy impact on DCCB current, energy, and voltage. This section evaluates more cases to find the range of error of models under realistic conditions. To achieve this, a PP fault along cable 1 is applied as it causes a high fault current in a symmetrical monopole system, resulting in a faster discharge of MMC energy. It is assumed that the fault resistance ranges from $R_F = [0.01, 10] \Omega$, and the line inductance $L_{dc} = [0, 50, 100, 150, 200] \text{ mH}$. The fault location is at $p = [1, 50, 99]\%$ along the line. In total, 30 cases are considered for each local and remote MMC. The results for local and remote MMC are presented in Fig. 6.

According to Fig. 3.6 (upper), model M_1 demonstrates better accuracy, with errors below 2% across all measured variables, compared to M_2 and M_3 . Model M_2 exhibits maximum errors of approximately 8%, 14%, and 25% for current, energy, and voltage of the CB1, respectively. In contrast, model M_3 shows errors exceeding 100%, indicating significantly reduced accuracy. Additionally, a visual comparison shows that the variance error for models M_3 and M_2 is higher than that of model M_0 . Fig. 6 (lower) shows a similar trend to the remote MMC models, but with less impact on accuracy. The maximum error for model M_1 remains below 2% across all variables. For model M_2 , the error rates are 5%, 7%, and 25% for I_{CB} , E_{MOV} , and V_{CB} , respectively. As expected, M_3 exhibits the highest error. The results presented in Fig. 6 underscore the necessity for an accurate model for local MMCs. The model of the remote converter has much less influence.

3.4 Conclusion

This chapter offers an approach to determine the accuracy requirements of component models used in HVDC protection studies. Firstly, it estimates

Figure 3.6: Impact of local (upper fig) and remote (lower fig) MMC models on parameters accuracy; error of I_{CB} , E_{MOV} , and voltage under various fault parameters ($R_f=[0.01, 10]$ and location $p=[1, 50, 99]$ %) and $L_{dc}=[0, 50, 100, 150, 200]$ mH compared to the model M_0 .

an accuracy requirement for protection studies based on i) a cost-based approach, and ii) a performance-based approach analysis, which recommends guidelines for selecting models. Secondly, it investigated the influence of the MMC model accuracy requirements for DCCB sizing. This was achieved by performing a sensitivity analysis of key DCCB parameters, such as current, voltage, and energy, with respect to different system and fault conditions. The analysis included both local and remote MMCs and benchmarked the results against a detailed model. The accuracy requirement varies depending on the stage of the studies, including conceptual system-level studies to component-level studies, becoming increasingly stringent as the final stages approach. The results show that, when using simplified models, a larger margin could be needed (due to a higher inaccuracy), which may not so useful for detailed component-level studies. Furthermore, the inaccuracy of the local MMC model has a more significant impact than the remote MMC, highlighting the necessity for more precise modelling of the local one.

This study considered an example of a 3-terminal HVDC to assess the accuracy impact of MMC, along with the adjacent cable. The simulation results were provided for a symmetrical monopole system, but further analysis may be needed for other configurations. To ensure broader applica-

bility and deeper insights, a comprehensive sensitivity analysis should be performed, covering a wide range of system and fault parameters. This can be complemented by exploring additional scenarios, including various system configurations and different DCCB technologies with diverse operating times etc.

Chapter 4

Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies

The content in this chapter is based on the following paper:

- A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. Van Hertem, “Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies,” in 22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission, Berlin, Germany, April 2026. [2]

4.1 Introduction

The industry looks towards large-scale HVDC grids to transmit energy across Europe [27] and achieve much of the necessary increase in electricity transmission capacity [28]. Specific configurations, such as electrical energy hubs [29], [30], are expected to result in complex configurations with multiple converters in close proximity. Moving from point-to-point (P2P) HVDC systems to multiterminal systems is expected to yield significant operational and economic benefits [27]. When designing the HVDC grid, dynamic validation is typically performed in electromagnetic transient (EMT) time-domain simulation [31]. Different types of studies, from design, validation and commissioning, require increasingly extensive EMT simulations. The models for these simulations must be representative of the phenomena under study, whilst not being overly computationally expensive [32]. As HVDC grids continue to expand, it becomes increasingly important to identify which aspects of the system require detailed modelling and which can be simplified without compromising accuracy. Additionally, detailed component mod-

els, such as converter models, may not always be available for all parts of the network, as future HVDC multiterminal systems are expected to be multi-vendor and to undergo system expansion [33].

HVDC grids undergo different stages when a DC short-circuit fault occurs, including four main stages: pre-fault, during-fault, grid restoration, and post-fault [34]. However, DC protection studies are mainly focused on during a fault and grid restoration. An example of a protection study is protection component sizing, which is mainly based on the fault response stage and has a shorter time scale than the recovery stage [4],[35]. Hence, it is needed to have a model that is representative of these stages and high transient phenomena, such as the travelling wave effect. Additionally, protection design in multiterminal HVDC grids, such as component sizing, is expected to be affected mainly by nearby Modular Multilevel Converters (MMC) rather than by those located far from the under study area. This indicates that a simplified model can be used for those MMCs. However, it is necessary to determine under which conditions a simplified model can be used for that MMC and the boundaries of areas beyond the direct area of interest for a particular study, so-called remote zone.

Protection studies of large multiterminal systems could be categorised into system-level and component-level analysis [6]. ‘System-level’ refers to aspects such as system topology design and component placement, which necessitate high-level studies like power flow, often employing simplified models, e.g., the steady-state model. On the other hand, ‘component-level’ refers to specific studies that focus on the specification of a component, including the design of protection algorithms and component sizing, such as DCCB. These studies are typically performed using EMT simulations to represent the real system with sufficient accuracy for the phenomena under study [8].

Regarding MMC models, various levels of fidelity exist. Type-3 models (switching-function based) are significantly more computationally demanding than Type-4 (Thévenin-equivalent) and Type-5 (average) models [32]. Type-6 represents a reduced-order dynamic model [11], offering a considerably simpler representation compared to the higher-fidelity types. A further simplified approach is to model the MMC as a voltage or current source; however, the suitability of such simplifications depends on the specific application and requirements.

Building on this challenge, this chapter addresses how to determine the appropriate level of modelling detail for converters located in remote parts of HVDC grids. Specifically, it proposes a method to identify the model requirements of MMCs in the remote zone of HVDC grids. The proposed approach employs an analytical approximation of the line current to determine the converter model requirements using boundary conditions (BC).

The remote zone is then characterised as the region of the system that satisfies these BC, allowing a decision on the level of detail of the MMC model for that area. The main contributions and features of this chapter are 1) to analyse and elaborate on the impact of the remote converter on the local zone, and 2) to identify and analytically approximate the boundary conditions for the remote converter.

The remainder of this chapter is structured as follows. Section 4.2 presents the analytical methodology used for estimating the model requirements. Section 4.3 evaluates the proposed method through EMT simulations.

4.2 Model requirements for remote MMC

The impact of MMC in the remote zone is likely related to the characteristics of the cables adjacent to the interested zone and the line inductance between the two areas. For instance, under certain conditions, such as a long line length, the contribution of the MMC in the remote zone to the under-study zones, so-called the local zone, could be reduced compared to a short line over a particular time scale. Therefore, possibly reduced models can be used in the remote zone. The model requirements for remote MMC can be specified by BC between the remote and local zones. Once these BC are identified and satisfied, the MMC can be characterised as a remote MMC. The impact of a converter model on fault current can be evaluated by analysing the converter's fault-current contribution to the local zone. The primary factor contributing to this is the magnitude of the current within a time window of interest. Other variables can also be used to evaluate the impact of the converter model, such as cable-end voltage or bus voltage. However, converter current is straightforward to measure and assess because it can be readily distinguished from contributions from other components, such as cable discharge current or other MMCs. On the other hand, voltage is affected by factors such as cable discharge current and other MMC currents and cannot be easily assigned to a certain MMC.

In general, a time window requirement for any study depends on the phenomena under study and their frequency range [36]. This time window requirement is relatively short for certain HVDC protection studies, HVDC protection algorithms, and HVDC circuit breakers. Therefore, it may impose less strict constraints on the model requirements. In other words, suppose that HVDC protection algorithms require a typical time window range of 0.1 to 2 ms [37], while for component sizing, such as DCCB, a typical range of 2 to 5 ms only considering up to opening time (hybrid breaker) [38]. The latter imposes hard constraints on when using a simple model for the remote zone.

Figure 4.1: Schematic of an example of HVDC grid

4.2.1 Conditions allowing use of reduced order models

To determine the boundaries of the remote zone, an example of a multiterminal HVDC grid, illustrated in Fig. 4.1, is considered. The system is simulated in PSCAD, where type 5 models are used for all three MMC (unless specified) with a time step of 10 μ s. Also, the frequency-dependent model is used for the line. It is assumed that the protection study focuses on Line 1 (as the local zone), so in the local zone, a detailed model, such as type 4 or 5, is implied (for both MMCs in P2P connection). The aim is to identify the BC for the MMC that is adjacent to the local zone through at least one line. It is also assumed that a line inductor is placed at each end of the line to keep the method generic. However, only the interested DCCB in the local zone is shown in the system.

To illustrate the impact of remote MMC on the local zone, it is assumed that a fault occurs on Line 1, as illustrated in Fig. 4.2, where lines 3 to m are not considered, as it would be the worst condition for the contribution of convert RC (more explanation in the following analysis). The contribution of the converter RC, which is connected to the local zone through line 2, to the circuit breaker current (I_{CB}) begins to increase after a certain time delay. This initial delay corresponds to the propagation time of the traveling wave (TW) along line 2 (Δt_{TW}), which depends on the line length and the TW propagation speed, which itself depends on physical properties and cross-section of the cable or overhead line (OHL). Following this delay, the current contribution from RC depends mainly on the inductance of the fault current path and the voltage difference between the local and remote bus. Additionally, the cable that is adjacent to the local bus contributes to the fault current, but the exact magnitude is not directly of interest for this converter modelling assessment. These effects are observable during a specific time window, as expressed in (4.1). The duration of this time window depends on the physical parameters and layout of the electrical system. In the next step, the allowable time window duration is used as input to determine

Figure 4.2: Example of the contributions of the remote and local MMCs to the fault current, illustrating the limits on Δt and ΔI .

which system properties the remote MMC contribution falls within.

$$\Delta t = \Delta t_{TW} + \Delta t_R \quad (4.1)$$

As time progresses, the fault current contribution from the MMC adjacent to the interested zone increases gradually. This implies that, for a particular system and a small time window, RC may have little or no influence on the fault current in the area of interest. In other words, there exists a time interval (Δt) during which the change in current (ΔI) is negligible, as illustrated in Fig. 4.2, depending on the objectives of the target study. Based on this observation, the impact of the RC can be assessed, and the appropriate level of model detail can be determined. For example, in the nonunit DC protection algorithm studies that focus on very short time windows (typically less than 1 ms), the RC has a negligible influence on the transient response in the local zone, provided that the line adjacent to the interested zone is sufficiently long. In such cases, the transient response of the RC can be ignored. However, not all studies consider such short time windows. For instance, protection component design and sizing, such as that of DC circuit breakers (DCCBs), may require longer simulation periods, during which the influence of RC transients may not be fully neglected. In this study, the recovery and post-fault stages are not considered, as these stages are expected to require detailed modelling for all MMCs in the system, and a reduced model may not be representative, as suitable control of MMC is needed.

As shown in (4.1) and Fig. 4.2, the first term of the time window corresponds to the travelling wave (TW) delay on the line that is adjacent to the local bus. Following a fault on Line 1, the current (or voltage) wave requires a time Δt_{TW} to propagate along the line. This delay can be estimated with

sufficient accuracy using (4.2), where l represents the line length and ν denotes the TW propagation speed. This time delay depends on the line length and the parameters and geometry of the cable or OHL [39].

$$\Delta t_{TW} \simeq \frac{l}{\nu} \quad (4.2)$$

The second term of (4.1) corresponds to the fault current rise time. When a fault occurs in the HVDC grid, the fault current increases rapidly. However, the presence of DC-side inductance (L_{dc}) limits the rate of this rise. When L_{dc} is relatively large compared to the inductance of the cable or OHL, the rise time can be approximated using (4.3).

$$\Delta t_R \simeq \frac{L_{eq} \cdot \Delta I_{RC}}{V_{eq}} \quad (4.3)$$

Here, $L_{eq} = \sum_{i=1}^N L_{dc}^i + lL_L$, where N represents the number of inductors in the fault path along the adjacent line to local bus, l is the line length, and L_L is the cable/OHL inductance (mH/km). The term ΔI_{RC} denotes the current contribution from the remote MMC, which is the input and is specified based on the study requirements. The voltage difference between the two local and remote buses is measured across the line as $V_{eq} = V_R - V_L$. Upon fault occurrence and before reaching the TW to the remote zone bus, the voltage at this bus can be assumed equal to the pre-fault value, $V_R \simeq V_0$. In contrast, the voltage at the local bus, V_L , can be approximated using (4.4), considering a close-in fault at the beginning of the line as a worst-case scenario, as it results in the shortest Δt .

$$V_L \simeq L_{CB} \frac{\Delta I_{CB}}{\Delta t} \quad (4.4)$$

Here, L_{CB} is assumed to represent the DC inductance on Line 1 terminal and is given a distinct notation to differentiate it from the DC inductance of the line, L_{dc} . When L_{CB} has a relatively small value, the difference between local bus voltage V_L and remote bus voltage V_R is higher than when it has a large value. The large difference between the two voltage buses results in the minimum value of Δt_R . Moreover, the circuit breaker current can be expressed as $I_{CB} = \sum_{j=1}^m I_{AD}^j + I_{LC}$, where I_{AD} denotes the current in the lines and I_{LC} is the current contribution from the local MMC. This relation indicates that, for a given L_{CB} , increasing the number of lines adjacent to the interested zone would be expected to lead to a larger Δt_R . In addition, a longer line length increases the discharge current of the line, which in turn contributes to a prolonged rise time of remote MMC (Δt_R). Considering (4.1) to (4.4) the final BC can be approximated as follows:

$$\Delta t \simeq \frac{1}{a}l + \frac{1}{b}L_{dc} \quad (4.5)$$

Figure 4.3: Conceptual overview of BC for remote MMC

where,

$$\frac{1}{a} \triangleq \frac{1}{\nu} + \frac{L_L \Delta I_{RC}}{V_R - V_L}, \quad \frac{1}{b} \triangleq \frac{N \Delta I_{RC}}{V_R - V_L}$$

Table 4.1: Example of inputs, parameters, and outputs

Inputs		System parameters		Outputs (BC)
Δt (ms)	2, 5	ν (km/ms)	178	L_{dc} (mH)
ΔI_{RC} (pu)	0.1, 0.5	$V_R \simeq V_0$ (kV)	320 (per pole)	l (km)
ΔI_{CB} (pu)	2.5, 4	L_L (mH/km)	0.2	
		N	2 (per pole)	
		L_{CB} (mH)	10, 100	

In (4.5), the parameters can be grouped into three categories, as summarised in Table 4.1. The first group corresponds to the inputs defined by the target study, where Δt and ΔI_{RC} are known, which are the so-called ‘current-time window’ limits. The current-time window limits depend on the protection strategy adopted for the HVDC grid, the component technologies (e.g., DCCB), and the study constraints and aims. To illustrate the application of the methodology, examples of parameters are provided in Table 4.1. In this example, considering a DC relay study, thresholds of $\Delta t \leq 2$ ms and $\Delta I_{RC} \leq 0.5$ pu could be used, whereas for DCCB sizing, these values may be set to 5 ms and 0.1 pu, respectively. The value of I_{CB} depends on the current contributions from both the local MMC and the lines adjacent to the local bus. This value can be either estimated analytically or obtained from EMT simulations.

The second group of parameters, listed in the second column of Table 4.1, corresponds to the system parameters, which are assumed to be known. For instance, given the cable or OHL parameters, the TW propagation speed (ν) can be calculated or extracted directly from the Line Constants Program in PSCAD. Finally, the third group represents the output, such that converter

requirements can be determined according to electrical topology and configuration.

Fig. 4.3 illustrates a conceptual overview of a BC, which is divided into two zones. The high-impact zone or local zone corresponds to the combinations of l and L_{dc} that cause the remote MMC current to exceed the current-time window limits (Δt and ΔI_{RC}) shown in Fig. 4.2. In contrast, the low-impact zone or remote zone satisfies the limits of the remote MMC for a given target study.

Several conclusions can be drawn from Fig. 4.3. First, increasing the current-time window duration (Δt) results in a broader high-impact zone with respect to l and L_{dc} . Moreover, the parameters a and b in (4.5) directly influence the BC; higher values of these parameters lead to a wider high-impact zone. For instance, increasing the local bus voltage (V_L) due to the large value of fault current (I_{CB}) and/or L_{CB} in (4.4), results in small values for parameters a and b . As a consequence, the boundary line in Fig. 4.3 moves downward and shrinks the local zone area. On the other hand, a small threshold value for ΔI_{RC} leads to the BC line moving above and broadening the local impact zone. The duration of the current-time window (Δt) also directly affects the BC line, so a large time window limit causes the BC line to move above. Additionally, as expected, TW affects only the parameter a and its corresponding parameters, i.e, the length of the line.

4.2.2 Decision on remote MMC model

The generic BC diagram in Fig. 4.3 indicates that, for parameter combinations above the blue line, this part of the system lies within the low-impact zone. The methodology indicates that in this region, the remote MMC has little or no influence on the transient response of local variables within the defined time window, given the approximation. Therefore, a simplified model is expected to be sufficient to represent the pre-fault condition, such as a reduced model or even a current (voltage) source. However, a detailed model is expected to be necessary if the part system falls within the local zone.

4.3 Validation of model selection requirement

Based on the analytical approximation to determine the model requirement, time-domain validation will now be performed to investigate the assumptions made and the analytical analysis. To illustrate this, a monopolar cable-based multi-terminal system is considered (Fig. 4.1), where line 3 to line m are normally not considered unless it is mentioned, with parameters shown in Table 4.1. The cable is modeled as a frequency-dependent (Phase) Model [13] with generic parameters. The MMC is modelled as a detailed Type 4

as described in [32]. As the system-level aspects are considered for these protection studies, this type of model provides sufficient accuracy [40]. Additionally, internal overcurrent protection blocks the MMC during a fault, as we consider a half-bridge MMC, but likely the methodology is not affected by the MMC's technology.

4.3.1 Study case for model selection requirement

As a starting point, it is necessary to define the allowable current–time window limits shown in Fig. 4.2 (yellow region). These limits enable the identification of system conditions (layout, electrical parameters, etc.) that satisfy the criteria and therefore fall within the remote zone. Conversely, if the conditions do not satisfy these limits, the corresponding section should be classified as a local zone, and the simplified MMC model is not recommended. The first limit is the duration of the current-time window (Δt), and the second limit is the maximum allowable current (ΔI_{RC}) that the remote MMC can feed to the fault location in a way that its impact can be neglected. Naturally, both limits depend on the type and objectives of the study.

Several case studies are considered for different values of current-window limits and system parameters. As mentioned, the allowable duration can be set based on the type of study of interest; for instance, for DC protection algorithm studies, such as a non-unit protection algorithm, the expected time duration can be less than 1–2 ms. While for other studies, i.e. protection component sizing, such as DCCB sizing, a longer duration for Δt is expected. In this example, for these two types of studies, Δt is set to 2 and 5 ms, respectively. Additionally, ΔI_{RC} is assumed to be 10% and 50% of the nominal current of the converter. It is worth noting that these are examples to illustrate the application of the method; any values appropriate to the study's needs can be used for these limits. An analysis shows that a high value of Δt and a lower value of ΔI_{RC} impose strict constraints on BC.

Table 4.2: BC parameters for a given input and system parameters

	Inputs				BC parameters	
	Δt (ms),	ΔI_{RC} (%)	L_{CB} (mH),	ΔI_{CB} (pu)	a	b
Case 1	2	50	100	5	118	35
Case 2	5	50	100	8	141	70
Case 3	2	10	100	5	162	175
Case 4	5	10	100	8	169	350
Case 5	2	50	10	8	158	140
Case 6	5	50	10	12	159	148
Case 7	2	10	10	8	158	140
Case 8	5	10	10	12	159	148

Figure 4.4: Boundary conditions of the remote MMC for the different cases in Table 4.2, based on the analytical approximation

Considering parameters in Table 4.2, using (4.5), the BC parameters are approximated and listed in Table 4.1. It is worth noting that the fault current passing through the circuit breaker depends on the system configuration and parameters, such as the number of cables adjacent to the local bus, L_{CB} , and the time following the fault. The circuit breaker current change, ΔI_{CB} , can be obtained from EMT simulations. For example, considering a fault on line 1 located in front of the DCCB and assuming the maximum pre-fault power flow as the worst-case scenario, the peak value of ΔI_{CB} depends on the local-line inductance (L_{CB}). When $L_{CB} = 10$ mH, the maximum ΔI_{CB} is approximately 4 pu (8 kA) at $\Delta t = 2$ ms and 6 pu (12 kA) at $\Delta t = 5$ ms. For $L_{CB} = 100$ mH, these values decrease to about 2.5 pu (5 kA) and 4 pu (8 kA), respectively, as shown in Fig. 4.2.

Fig. 4.4 illustrates the BC for the parameters listed in Table 4.2. It approximately distinguishes the low-impact zone from the high-impact zone for the specified current–time window limits. As evident from (4.5), increasing the duration of Δt requires higher values of l and L_{dc} on the cable adjacent to the local bus (bus L in Fig. 4.1). Comparing Case 1 and Case 2 clearly shows that the BC line shifts upward (i.e., the high-impact zone becomes wider) when Δt increases from 2 to 5 ms. Similarly, ΔI_{RC} has a comparable influence on the BC. By comparing Case 1 and Case 3, it becomes evident that reducing the remote MMC current contribution widens the high-impact zone. The same trend is observed for Case 2 and Case 4, where the window duration is longer.

Moreover, the BC is affected not only by the current–time window limits but also by system parameters such as L_{CB} . Cases 5 to 8 consider $L_{CB} =$

10 mH, whereas in Cases 1 to 4 it is 100 mH, while all other current–time window limits remain the same. For instance, comparing Case 1 ($L_{CB} = 100$ mH) and Case 5 ($L_{CB} = 10$ mH), it is clear that a lower value of L_{CB} results in a wider high-impact zone, requiring longer cable lengths and larger inductances to sufficiently neglect the remote MMC’s influence.

To evaluate the accuracy of the approximated BC, several test points (T_1 to T_9) are selected from Fig. 4.5 (a) and validated using EMT simulations. In this validation, only Cases 1 and 2 are presented. However, other cases are also valid but not plotted here. For Case 1, test points T_1 , T_2 , and T_3 are expected to remain just below the threshold of $\Delta I_{RC} = 0.5$ (i.e., within the low-impact zone) at $\Delta t = 2$ ms, while T_5 is expected to lie well below the corresponding current–time window limits. This behavior is confirmed by the results presented in plot (b). On the other hand, test point T_4 lies within the high-impact zone, meaning that under these system parameters, remote MMC current contribution cannot meet the corresponding current–time window limits. This is clear from the Fig. 4.5 (b), where the current of the remote MMC exceeds the threshold of $\Delta I_{RC} = 0.5$ before the end of the set time window ($\Delta t = 2$ ms). On the other hand, test point T_5 , located between the BC of Case 1 and Case 2, the simulation result shows that the current exceeds its threshold approximately 4.3 ms after the fault, falling between meeting Case 1 limits (2 ms) and not satisfying Case 2 limits (5 ms), thus validating the results shown in plot (a). The same analysis applies to the remaining test points. Furthermore, the results show that the approximated BC line is slightly higher than the exact values obtained through EMT simulation. Meaning that the analytical method slightly overestimates the BC. For instance, considering T_6 and T_7 in plot (a), they are exactly on BC, and it is expected that, in the EMT simulation, their corresponding current should be just below the current limit (ΔI_{RC}). However, according to the results in plot (b), the currents at $t = 6$ ms (equivalent to $\Delta I_{RC} = 5$ ms) are much below the threshold. This is because the approximated analytical solution does not account for the cable discharge current. For long cable lengths and consequently higher discharge current, the actual boundary is slightly bent downward.

4.3.2 Impact of system configuration and parameters

As the method is based on the fault current contribution to determine the impact of remote MMC, it is applied to configurations where the fault leads to high fault currents. This means that it is applicable for all configurations, regardless of the type of fault, except for pole-to-ground faults in symmetrical monopole configurations, which result in overvoltage [41]. Regarding system voltage, fault type, and the number of line inductance on each line,

Figure 4.5: Boundary condition evaluation; (a) Identified BC based on the analytical approximation Case 1 and 2 as specified in Table 4.2, (b) demonstration of the BC using EMT simulations at selected test points (T_1 to T_9) to verify compliance with the defined thresholds

are already included in (4.5) and serve as parameters. For example, a system with 525 kV voltage leads to higher values for a and b compared to a 320 kV system. The effect of the number of DC inductances depends on the protection strategy; fully protective schemes offer the maximum number of DC inductances per-pole, while this is lower for partially selective protection, as not all lines may have their DCCB and line inductance. Additionally, the BC parameters, a and b , are not affected by the type of fault, since from (4.3) the ratio of L_{eq}/V_{eq} remains the same for PP and Pg faults.

In Fig. 4.6, further evaluation of the approximated BC is provided, similar to what is done in Fig. 4.4. This involves selecting a test point on the BC, corresponding to a specific combination of system parameters, and validating it through EMT simulation. The results show that the approximated BC are slightly higher than the exact values obtained through EMT simulation. This is because the approximated analytical solution does not account for the adjacent cable discharge current, disregards the voltage drop along the line, and uses a first-order approximation. Test points T_{17} to T_{20} are estimated to be in the high-impact zone (meaning that the current exceeds the ΔI_{RC} limit before $\Delta t = 5$ ms), while they are actually placed in the low-impact zone, due to the adjacent cable discharge current and line inductance.

Figure 4.6: Further BC evaluation

4.3.3 Impact of adjacent cable/OHL on local zone

The impact of multiple lines connected to the local bus on the current contribution of the remote MMC can be inferred from (4.4) and (4.5). When a fault occurs in the local zone, neighbouring cables discharge capacitive current into the fault location, increasing the DCCB current and causing higher voltage on the local bus (V_L). According to (4.5), a higher value of local bus (V_L) yields lower values of parameters a and b , thereby narrowing the high-impact zone. EMT simulation is performed to validate this analysis. As illustrated in Fig. 4.7, increasing the number of cables prolongs the rise time of the remote MMC current and reduces the remote converter fault current contribution, as can be inferred from (4.4) and (4.5). In other words, the minimum number of adjacent cables gives the worst-case/most conservative assessment. On the other hand, since OHL has a lower shunt capacitance than cable, its effect on the remote MMC current is less significant, as can be seen from Fig. 4.7. In this comparison, both cable and OHL are assumed to have the same length of 300 km.

Figure 4.7: Impact of the number of adjacent lines on the contribution of remote MMC to the fault in the local zone (a) cable, (b) OHL

4.4 Conclusion

In large-scale HVDC grids, depending on the type of protection study, it may not be necessary to model all MMCs with the same level of detail; simplified models could be used for remote areas, during a specific time window. For instance, with a cable length of 350 km and a 2 ms time window, the converter is located in a remote area. On the other hand, detailed models may be necessary in the local area. This enhances simulation efficiency by reducing the simulation size without compromising accuracy. The main challenge, however, is defining the boundaries between the remote and local zones. This chapter presents a straightforward analytical approximation for setting these boundary conditions, based on line inductance and line length, and validates the method through EMT simulations across different cases. The analysis and simulation results indicate that, for larger line inductances and/or longer line lengths (e.g. 350 km), the contribution of remote MMCs to the local fault current remains below the specified threshold (e.g. 0.1 pu) within the given time window (e.g. 2 ms). The results also confirmed that the analytical method is slightly conservative, yielding boundary conditions slightly higher than those observed in the simulations.

Chapter 5

Identification of critical simulation cases

5.1 Critical cases for protection design

For protection component-level design, it is essential to identify the critical simulation cases and conditions and base the design on them. This approach ensures that the selected design parameters remain valid across all relevant scenarios while minimizing the total number of cases that need to be evaluated.

5.1.1 Critical converter

Within each protection zone, a critical converter that reaches its overcurrent limit faster than the others for out-of-zone faults must be identified. According to the methodology provided in [3], the critical converter in each zone is identified as the one requiring the largest inductor. For instance, if two converters in a protection zone have the same parameters, the one connected directly to the DCCB or via the shortest line is the critical one due to the low fault wave propagation delay and low cable discharge current [42].

5.1.2 Critical power flows

The identification of critical power flows in the system is relatively straightforward. The power flows that result in the maximum loading of the critical converter in rectifier mode, and the maximum loading for the DCCB under study are considered critical power flows with regard to a DC-side fault [3].

Figure 5.1: A test HVDC system for identifying critical fault location

Figure 5.2: Critical fault location along the cable according to cable voltage envelope (\bar{U}_m)

5.1.3 Critical fault type and location

The critical fault type depends on system configuration and grounding options, e.g., a pole-to-ground (P-g) fault in a bipolar system is a possible fault for a cable-based system with zero fault resistance [41], [43]. The worst-case fault location is the one that results in a rapid rise and a high peak fault current. Due to the traveling-wave effect, the reflection coefficient, the cable parameters, and fault neutralization time (t_n), it is possible that a critical fault location lies along the cable in the other zone [44]. To find the critical fault location along the cable, a fault is applied at various locations. Then, the cable voltage envelope can be estimated by taking the minimum of the average voltage as $\bar{U}_m = \min(\bar{U}_C, 0)$, where \bar{U}_C is the average of cable end voltage at bus C (U_C) as shown in Fig 5.1 [3].

As shown in Fig. 5.2, the critical fault location depends on the fault neutralization time (t_n) and the critical time (t_c) where $\bar{U}_m \leq 0$. For $t_n \geq t_c$, a

terminal fault (0 km) results in a minimum voltage envelope ($\bar{U}_m = 0$) and a high fault current after the critical time (e.g., $t_c = 1.8$ ms in the illustrated case with example cable parameters). However, if $t_n < t_c$, a non-terminal fault should be considered as the critical fault location, and the minimum cable end voltage (\bar{U}_C) at t_n instant correspond to critical fault location along the cable. This critical time (t_c) depends on parameters such as cable characteristics and the DC inductor, and it must be determined for each system using a similar approach as shown in Fig. 5.2. It is worth noting that although a large DC inductor can result in smaller \bar{U}_m and increase the t_c , it further limits the fault current. In summary:

- Different fault locations along the cable are simulated in EMT-type software, as shown in Fig. 5.1, and the average cable-end voltage (\bar{U}_C) is calculated for each case (as a post processing step, voltages needs to be aligned by shifting).
- The voltage envelope (\bar{U}_m) and the corresponding critical time (t_c) are then estimated.
- Based on the neutralization time of the protection system (e.g., the DCCB technology):
 - If $t_n \geq t_c$, the terminal fault is considered the critical fault location.
 - If $t_n < t_c$, the critical fault location is located somewhere along the cable. In this case, the minimum value of \bar{U}_C at t_n corresponds to the critical fault location.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In conclusion, this report presents methods to improve the efficiency of EMT-type simulations for HVDC protection studies while maintaining the required modeling accuracy. The work demonstrates that the appropriate selection of MMC models can significantly reduce computational complexity without compromising the accuracy of protection studies. In particular, simplified models can be used for remote converters, whereas higher modeling accuracy is more important for local MMCs. In addition, the proposed methodology for identifying critical simulation cases reduces the number of required study scenarios, thereby improving the efficiency of protection design and validation processes for HVDC grids and electrical energy hubs.

Bibliography

- [1] A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. Van Hertem, "Modelling accuracy requirements for hvdc protection design studies," in *2025 IEEE PES Innovative Smart Grid Technologies Conference Europe (ISGT Europe)*, 2025, pp. 1–5. doi: [10.1109/ISGTEurope64741.2025.11305690](https://doi.org/10.1109/ISGTEurope64741.2025.11305690)
- [2] A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. V. Hertem, "Remote mmc model selection method in hvdc grids for protection studies," in *22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission*, Berlin, Germany, Apr. 2026.
- [3] A. Mohammadi, M. V. Deyck, G. Chaffey, and D. V. Hertem, *Hybrid analytical–emt method for hvdc protection system component-level design*, 2026. arXiv: [2605.11174](https://arxiv.org/abs/2605.11174) [eess.SY]. [Online]. Available: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2605.11174>
- [4] M. Abedrabbo, W. Leterme, and D. Van Hertem, "Systematic approach to HVDC circuit breaker sizing," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 288–300, 2020. doi: [10.1109/TPWRD.2019.2922253](https://doi.org/10.1109/TPWRD.2019.2922253)
- [5] A. Bertinato and G. D. De Freitas, "Assessment of protection strategy options for future DC grids," in *Proc. CIGRE Session*, Paris, France, 2020.
- [6] M. Van Deyck, A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. Van Hertem, "Review of (co-)design methods for HVDC protection systems," in *CIGRE NRCC International Symposium*, Trondheim, 2025.
- [7] J. Beerten, S. Cole, and R. Belmans, "Generalized steady-state VSC MTDC model for sequential AC/DC power flow algorithms," *IEEE Transactions on Power Systems*, vol. 27, no. 2, pp. 821–829, May 2012.
- [8] CIGRE, "Modelling and simulation studies to be performed during the lifecycle of HVDC systems," CIGRE, Tech. Rep. TB 563, 2013.
- [9] N. Ahmed, L. Ängquist, S. Norrga, A. Antonopoulos, L. Harnefors, and H.-P. Nee, "A computationally efficient continuous model for the modular multilevel converter," *IEEE Journal of Emerging and Selected Topics in Power Electronics*, vol. 2, no. 4, pp. 1139–1148, 2014.

- [10] W. Leterme and D. Van Hertem, "Reduced modular multilevel converter model to evaluate fault transients in DC grids," in *12th IET International Conference on Developments in Power System Protection (DPSP 2014)*, Copenhagen, Denmark, Mar. 2014, pp. 1–6.
- [11] W. Leterme, J. Beerten, and D. Van Hertem, "Equivalent circuit for half-bridge MMC dc fault current contribution," in *2016 IEEE International Energy Conference (ENERGYCON)*, Apr. 2016.
- [12] M. Zaja, D. Jovicic, L. Kunjumammed, K. Tahata, T. Inagaki, and S. Nee, "Generic and simplified HV DC circuit breaker models for grid-level studies," in *2020 IEEE Power & Energy Society General Meeting (PESGM)*, 2020.
- [13] A. Beddard and M. Barnes, "HVDC cable modelling for VSC-HVDC applications," in *2014 IEEE PES General Meeting | Conference & Exposition*, Jul. 2014.
- [14] H. Saad, P. Rault, M. Goertz, and S. Wenig, "Parameter sensitivity analysis on DC transients between MMC station and cable," *Electric Power Systems Research*, vol. 196, p. 107 277, Jul. 2021.
- [15] T. Karmokar, "Enhanced modelling and parameter determination of HVDC cables using practice-oriented methodology," *CIGRE Science and Engineering*, 2015.
- [16] W. Leterme, J. Beerten, and D. Van Hertem, "Nonunit protection of HVDC grids with inductive DC cable termination," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 31, no. 2, pp. 820–828, 2016.
- [17] C. Eckert, O. Isaksson, and C. Earl, "Design margins: A hidden issue in industry," *Design Science*, vol. 5, e9, Jan. 2019.
- [18] P. Düllmann, C. Brantl, C. Klein, and A. Moser, "Interdependencies in HVDC grid protection: Impact of converter parameters and controls on DC fault-ride-through capabilities and protection system design," *IET Generation, Transmission & Distribution*, vol. 17, no. 10, pp. 2356–2375, 2023.
- [19] PROMOTioN, "Preparation of cost-benefit analysis from a protection point of view," PROMOTioN, Tech. Rep. D4.7, 2020.
- [20] N. A. Belda and R. P. P. Smeets, "Test circuits for HVDC circuit breakers," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 32, no. 1, pp. 285–293, Feb. 2017.
- [21] CIGRE, "Guide for the development of models for HVDC converters in a HVDC grid," CIGRE, Tech. Rep. TB 657, 2014.

-
- [22] P. D. Judge et al., "Power-system level classification of voltage source HVDC converter stations based upon DC fault handling capabilities," *IET Renewable Power Generation*, vol. 13, no. 15, pp. 2899–2912, Nov. 2019.
- [23] U. N. Gnanarathna, A. M. Gole, and R. P. Jayasinghe, "Efficient modeling of modular multilevel HVDC converters (MMC) on electromagnetic transient simulation programs," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 26, no. 1, pp. 316–324, 2011.
- [24] A. Beddard and M. Barnes, "Modelling of MMC-HVDC systems – An overview," *Energy Procedia*, vol. 80, pp. 201–212, 2015.
- [25] CIGRE, "Technical requirements and specifications of state-of-the-art HVDC switching equipment," CIGRE, Paris, Tech. Rep. TB 682, 2017.
- [26] M. K. Bucher and C. M. Franck, "Comparison of fault currents in multiterminal HVDC grids with different grounding schemes," in *2014 IEEE PES General Meeting | Conference & Exposition*, Jul. 2014.
- [27] D. V. Hertem, O. Gomis-Bellmunt, and J. Liang, Eds., *HVDC Grids: For Offshore and Supergrid of the Future*. Hoboken, NJ, USA: Wiley, 2016.
- [28] ENTSO-E, "Vision: A power system for a carbon neutral europe," ENTSO-E, Tech. Rep., 2022.
- [29] G. Bastianel et al., "Review, definition and challenges of electrical energy hubs," *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*, 2026.
- [30] M. Useche-Arteaga, P. M. O. Gebraad, V. A. Lacerda, M. Cheah-Mane, B. Castro Valerio, and O. Gomis-Bellmunt, "Energy islands: Opportunities, challenges, and topologies," *IEEE Access*, vol. 13, pp. 194 366–194 381, 2025.
- [31] H. Saad, M. Vor Dem Berge, B. Marshall, and O. D. Adeuyi, "Overview on dynamic studies, tools, and models for high-voltage dc-offshore wind farm systems: Dynamic studies guidelines for offshore high-voltage dc systems," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 22, no. 5, pp. 60–72, Sep. 2024.
- [32] Cigre, "Guide for the development of models for HVDC converters in a HVDC grid," Cigre, Tech. Rep. TB 604, 2014.
- [33] M. Wang et al., "Review and outlook of HVDC grids as backbone of transmission system," *CSEE Journal of Power and Energy Systems*, vol. 7, no. 4, pp. 797–810, Jul. 2021.
- [34] PROMOTioN Workpackage 4, "Deliverable 4.2: Broad comparison of fault clearing strategies for DC grids," PROMOTioN, Tech. Rep., 2017.

- [35] D. Hart, A. Bertinato, P. Torwelle, and H. F. de Barros, "Impact of MMC temporary blocking functionality on DC grid protection design," in *22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission (ACDC Global 2025)*, Birmingham, UK, 2025.
- [36] P. Rault, "Dynamic modelling and control of multiterminal HVDC grids," Ph.D. dissertation, Ecole Centrale de Lille, Mar. 2014.
- [37] W. Leterme and D. V. Hertem, "Classification of fault clearing strategies for HVDC grids," in *Proc. CIGRÉ Symp.*, Lund, Sweden, 2015.
- [38] M. Callavik, A. Blomberg, J. Häfner, and B. Jacobson, "The hybrid HVDC breaker: An innovation breakthrough enabling reliable HVDC grids," ABB Grid Systems, ABB, Zürich, Switzerland, Tech. Rep., 2012.
- [39] B. Gustavsen, T. Noda, J. Naredo, F. Uribe, and J. Martinez-Velasco, *Power System Transients: Parameter Determination*. Taylor and Francis Group, 2010.
- [40] H. Saad et al., "Modular multilevel converter models for electromagnetic transients," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 29, no. 3, pp. 1481–1489, Jun. 2014.
- [41] W. Leterme, P. Tielens, S. De Boeck, and D. V. Hertem, "Overview of grounding and configuration options for meshed HVDC grids," *IEEE Transactions on Power Delivery*, vol. 29, no. 6, pp. 2467–2475, Dec. 2014.
- [42] A. Mohammadi, G. Chaffey, and D. Van Hertem, "Remote MMC model selection method in HVDC grids for protection studies," in *22nd IET International Conference on AC and DC Power Transmission*, Berlin, Germany, Apr. 2026.
- [43] W. Leterme, I. Jahn, P. Ruffing, et al., "Designing for high-voltage dc grid protection: Fault clearing strategies and protection algorithms," *IEEE Power and Energy Magazine*, vol. 17, no. 3, pp. 73–81, May 2019. DOI: [10.1109/MPE.2019.2903841](https://doi.org/10.1109/MPE.2019.2903841)
- [44] O. Cwikowski, B. Chang, M. Barnes, R. Shuttleworth, and A. Beddard, "Fault current testing envelopes for VSC HVDC circuit breakers," *IET Gener., Transm. Distrib.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 1393–1400, 2016.

etch.be

